

**KRANIAL NERVLAR KASALLIKLARINI TASHXISLASHDA
KOMPYUTER TOMOGRAFIYASI VA MAGNIT-REZONANS
TOMOGRAFIYANING IMKONIYATLARI.**

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Annotatsiya: Kranial nervlarning patologiyalarini aniqlashda aniq va ishonchli tashxis usullaridan foydalanish juda muhim. Kompyuter tomografiyasi (KT) va magnit-rezonans tomografiya (MRT) zamonaviy nur tashxis usullari bo‘lib, ularning har biri o‘ziga xos afzalliklarga ega. Ushbu texnologiyalar nervlarning anatomik va patologik holatini o‘rganishda keng qo‘llaniladi.

Kalit so‘zlar : kranial nervlar, kranial nerv kasalliklari, kompyuter tomografiya, magnit-rezonans tomografiya.

**CAPABILITIES OF COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY AND MAGNETIC
RESONANCE IMAGING
IN DIAGNOSING CRANIAL NERVE DISORDERS.**

Annotation: Accurate and reliable diagnostic methods are crucial for identifying cranial nerve pathologies. Computed Tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are modern radiological diagnostic tools, each with distinct

advantages. These technologies are widely utilized in studying the anatomical and pathological conditions of cranial nerves.

Keywords: cranial nerves, cranial nerve diseases, Computed tomography, Magnetic resonance imaging.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ И МАГНИТНО-РЕЗОНАНСНОЙ ТОМОГРАФИИ В ДИАГНОСТИКЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ЧЕРЕПНЫХ НЕРВОВ.

Аннотация: Использование точных и надежных методов диагностики играет важную роль в выявлении патологий черепных нервов. Компьютерная томография (КТ) и магнитно-резонансная томография (МРТ) являются современными методами лучевой диагностики, каждый из которых обладает своими уникальными преимуществами. Эти технологии широко применяются для изучения анатомического и патологического состояния нервов.

Ключевые слова: черепные нервы, заболевания черепных нервов, компьютерная томография, магнитно-резонансная томография.

Introduction

The human body has 12 pairs of cranial nerves that control motor and sensory functions of the head and neck. This article provides a pictorial overview of the imaging of cranial nerves, with a special focus on their anatomy and pathology. Radiologists and, specially, neuroradiologists should be familiar with the anatomy of each cranial nerve and should know clinical and imaging findings of their dysfunctions[4]. Although radiological findings are nonspecific in many cranial nerve pathologies, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with heavily T2-weighted three-dimensional (3D) steady-state free precession (SSFP) sequences, which have high spatial resolution and provide good contrast between cerebrospinal fluid and the cisternal segments of the cranial nerves, and contrast-enhanced T1-weighted sequences, facilitates the depiction of abnormalities. Computed tomography (CT) scans with bone window settings are

also quite useful for detecting cranial nerve pathologies, such as: agenesis/hypoplasia of the facial nerve canal and the geniculate ganglion fossa; fractures that extend through the skull base foramina in the context of trauma; enlargement or erosion of the skull base foramina caused by slow- or fast-growing cranial nerve tumors, respectively; and cranial nerve compression secondary to conditions that result in bone expansion and subsequent foraminal narrowing, including fibrous dysplasia[6].

Overview of cranial nerve anatomy

I - Olfactory nerve (sensory function): passes below each frontal lobe via the olfactory sulci and transmits impulses from the olfactory epithelium to the brain.

II - Optic nerve (sensory function): emerges from each globe as a thick fiber bundle that passes through the optic canal, and merges with the other optic nerve to form the optic chiasm.

III - Oculomotor nerve (motor and parasympathetic functions): arises from the interpeduncular fossa of the midbrain; passes along the lateral wall of the cavernous sinus and through the superior orbital fissure; innervates the levator palpebrae superioris and most extraocular muscles (including the superior, medial and inferior rectus muscles, as well as the inferior oblique muscles); and has parasympathetic functions, controlling the ciliary and sphincter pupillae muscles.

IV - Trochlear nerve (motor function): arises from the dorsal surface of the midbrain just below the inferior colliculus, surrounds the contralateral surface of the midbrain, passes along the lateral wall of the cavernous sinus and through the superior orbital fissure, and innervates the superior oblique muscles.

V - Trigeminal nerve (motor and sensory functions): arises from the anterolateral surface of the pons, passes below the tentorium cerebelli, arriving at Meckel's cave, where it splits into the ophthalmic, maxillary, and mandibular nerves, which pass through the superior orbital fissure, foramen rotundum, and foramen ovale, respectively, to exit the skull; enables mastication, carries proprioceptive and nociceptive afferents to the face and mouth, and innervates the tensor tympani, tensor

veli palatini, and mylohyoid muscles, as well as the anterior belly of the digastric muscle.

VI - Abducens nerve (motor function): arises from the pontomedullary junction, near the midline; crosses the petrous apex within Dorello's canal; ascends to pass through the cavernous sinus near the internal carotid arteries; exits through the superior orbital fissure and innervates the lateral rectus muscle.

VII - Facial nerve (motor, sensory, and parasympathetic functions): arises from the pons at the cerebellopontine angle; enters the internal auditory canals from an anterosuperior direction; passes through the temporal bones; exits through the stylomastoid foramen; controls facial expressions and taste sensation from the anterior two-thirds of the tongue and oral cavity; and regulates the function of the salivary glands (except the parotid gland), as well as that of the lacrimal, nasal, and palatine glands.

VIII - Vestibulocochlear nerve (sensory function): arise from the pons at the cerebellopontine angle; enters the internal auditory canals together with the facial nerve; splits into the cochlear nerve, in an anterior inferior direction, and the superior and inferior vestibular nerves, in a posterior direction; and carries afferents related to hearing and balance.

IX - Glossopharyngeal nerve (sensory, motor, and parasympathetic functions): arises from the medulla oblongata in the postolivary sulcus via a series of vertical rootlets lateral to the olivary body, above and along with those of the tenth and eleventh cranial nerves; carries sensory afferents to the oropharynx, posterior third of the tongue, carotid sinus, carotid body, and tympanic membrane; supplies motor innervation to the stylopharyngeus muscle; and provides parasympathetic innervation to the parotid gland.

X - Vagus nerve (sensory, motor, and parasympathetic functions): the longest of the cranial nerves, arising from the medulla oblongata via rootlets in the postolivary sulcus; exiting the posterior cranial fossa through the jugular foramen; descending in

the carotid sheath posterior to the internal jugular vein and internal/common carotid arteries; and dividing into its pharyngeal, thoracic, and abdominal branches.

XI - Spinal accessory nerve (motor function): arises from caudal region of the nucleus ambiguus via rootlets in the postolivary sulcus, below and along with those of the ninth and tenth cranial nerves, joining the latter, from which it is indistinguishable.

XII - Hypoglossal nerve (motor function): arises from the medulla via a series of vertical rootlets in the preolivary sulcus; enters the hypoglossal canal of the occipital bone; descends to the neck near the carotid sheath; passes lateral to the hyoglossus muscle to enter the tongue from below; and innervates all intrinsic and extrinsic muscles of the tongue, except the palatoglossus muscle, which is innervated by the tenth cranial nerve[6].

Cranial nerve diseases

Pathology of cranial nerves involves a wide spectrum of etiologies that includes primary or secondary neoplastic involvement, inflammation, infections, traumatic injuries, ischemic lesions, compression by adjacent structures, and congenital pathologies[4].

Neoplasms

Schwannoma is a benign nerve sheath tumor that originates from Schwann cells. Approximately 90% of intracranial schwannomas arise from the VIII cranial nerve with trigeminal involvement as the second most common (0.8–5%). Intracranial schwannomas can be associated with neurofibromatosis 2 (NF2), a genetic condition characterized by the presence of multiple schwannomas, meningiomas, and ependymomas. Patient with NF2 may have bilateral vestibular schwannomas or non-vestibular schwannomas. Imaging shows the slow growth of the tumor, with bone remodeling of neural foramen and deformation of the adjacent brain tissue. Features of end-organ compromise can be present. On CT, schwannomas have low-intermediate attenuation with variable enhancement. MR imaging findings include isohypointensity on T1-weighted sequences, high signal on T2-weighted sequences, and

marked enhancement on post-contrast images, eventually with unenhanced cystic spaces[2,4,5].

Traumatic diseases

Traumatic lesions of the cranial nerves are variable, depending on the length, course, and vascular supply of the nerve in question, as well its relationships with the surrounding bony and dural structures. Possible mechanisms of cranial nerve trauma include stretching, impingement, and transection. Such trauma may be iatrogenic and sometimes requires surgical repair. A combination of CT and MRI is usually required for a thorough assessment, and neuropathies resulting from recent trauma can show enhancement on contrast-enhanced T1-weighted images. Of all the cranial nerves, the third is the most commonly injured, such injury typically being due to contusion (at the petroclinoid ligament), tearing, or complete avulsion (at the interpeduncular fossa)[9]. High-resolution CT is the imaging modality of choice to detect skull base fractures and foraminal involvement. MRI may be useful to demonstrate intraneural edema or hemorrhage, especially on T2*-weighted sequences. Olfactory nerve may be involved in the closed injury of basal frontal lobe, with or without association of cribriform plate fracture[4].

Inflammation

The term optic neuritis (ON) usually refers to inflammatory process that involve optic nerve. Clinically, it presents with painful eye movements and visual loss. On MRI, the nerve appears swollen and hyperintense on T2-weighted sequences, with contrast enhancement best seen on fat-suppressed T1-weighted sequences. ON may be observed in autoimmune (for example multiple sclerosis and neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders) and systemic diseases (sarcoidosis, lupus erythematosus, Wegener disease, Sicca syndrome, Behcet disease). Particularly, in neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD), nerve involvement may be bilateral and more severe than in multiple sclerosis (MS). NMOSD is also characterized by involvement of spinal cord, with brain MRI features not suggestive for MS[4].

Infection

When the infectious diseases that can affect the cranial nerves are considered, it should be borne in mind that there has been a recent increase in the incidence of syphilis, and that the first sign of neurosyphilis can be involvement of one or more cranial nerves, in some cases mimicking other, more common, diseases such as schwannoma. Within the context of the epidemiology of Brazil, meningeal tuberculosis and leptospirosis also continue to be of concern, the latter being quite strongly associated with poor sanitation and flooding, especially during the summer[7]. Infectious meningitis may result from viral, bacterial, fungal, or parasitic infection. Viral infections, mostly related to Herpes simplex virus type 1, Cytomegalovirus, and Varicella zoster, may manifest with cranial nerve involvement and abnormal enhancement of the nerve on MRI. Bacterial meningitis is typically caused by Haemophilus Influenzae, Streptococcus pneumoniae, and Neisseria Meningitidis. Imaging is often normal, although MRI post-contrast sequences can demonstrate leptomeningeal enhancement. Intracranial Tuberculosis, typically in pediatric population, can manifest as leptomeningitis with involvement of cranial nerves. Cryptococcus neoformans is associated with the Cryptococcal meningitis, characterized by optic neuropathy. Necrosis of the optic nerve and chiasm by cryptococcal organism have been described. Rhinocerebral mucormycosis is fungal infection in immunocompromised patients, with sinonasal disease that may progress to the orbit and cavernous sinus. It can be complicated by vascular and perineural invasion and local thrombotic infarction. Cranial neuroschistosomiasis, less common than the spinal form, is characterized by a granulomatous reaction that leads to increase of intracranial pressure and focal neurologic signs. Lyme disease, caused by Borrelia burgdorferi, may involve any of the cranial nerves, with a predilection for the facial nerve, that appears thickened and enhanced[4].

Neurovascular compression

Arterial contact with the root entry zone or the proximal cisternal segment of a lower cranial nerve may cause neurovascular compression symptoms. In cases of

glossopharyngeal neuralgia with neurovascular compression, the most common related vessel is the posterior inferior cerebellar artery, followed by the vertebral artery, the anterior inferior cerebellar artery (AICA), and other vessels or combinations of vessels[5]. To explain more fully, neurovascular compression syndromes are caused by vascular structures (usually arteries) that directly contact the cisternal segment of a cranial nerve. Typically, the transition zone between the central and the peripheral myelin is the most vulnerable region of the nerve. Clinical presentation is variable and includes trigeminal and glossopharyngeal neuralgia, vestibular paroxysm, and hemifacial spasm. However, neurovascular compression should be evaluated only in the presence of specific clinical features. Also, nonhemorrhagic aneurysms may be associated to nerve dysfunction, for example in the case of vision loss due to compression of II nerve or optic chiasm by proximal internal carotid artery, and III, IV, or VI cranial nerves' palsy secondary to intracavernous aneurysm. Imaging may be useful to detect the displacement and the compression of a nerve by redundant arteries. Steady-state sequences and corresponding Time-of-Flight (TOF) or 3D T1-weighted gadolinium-enhanced images are very useful for diagnosis and preoperative evaluation[4].

Congenital diseases

Moebius syndrome is a congenital condition characterized by paresis of the sixth and seventh cranial nerves. It has a multifactorial etiology, the causes including hypoxic insult, genetic susceptibility, and iatrogenic factors such as the use of prostaglandin-1 during pregnancy. Individuals with Moebius syndrome can have craniofacial, cardiovascular and musculoskeletal defects, with or without other cranial nerve palsies, as well as abnormalities of the chest wall, spine, limbs, and soft tissues. Typical features of the syndrome include the following: facial diplegia of the upper and lower facial muscles; impaired abduction of both eyes; craniofacial and limb malformations; hypoglossia; and long tract signs. Findings on CT and MRI include various features: pontine and medullary hypoplasia; absence of the medial colliculus; calcification in the region of the abducens nuclei; depression of the fourth ventricle;

and absence of the hypoglossal prominence, suggestive of hypoglossal nuclei hypoplasia and cerebellar hypoplasia[6]. Furthermore, inherited neurometabolic disorders (INMDs) constitute a heterogeneous group of diseases that includes the so-called inborn errors of metabolism, leukodystrophies, mitochondrial diseases, and deposition diseases. Although INMDs are rare individually, they collectively account for a significant proportion of neurological diseases in children. The clinical and imaging findings of INMDs can be nonspecific and can overlap, making the diagnosis challenging. However, because there are treatments available for some INMDs, early diagnosis is fundamental in order to minimize or prevent neurological damage. Therefore, it is essential that neuroradiologists are able to recognize the imaging findings that can narrow the differential diagnosis. Magnetic resonance imaging is the modality of choice for the evaluation of various diseases of the central nervous system, including INMDs, being crucial for the localization, identification, and characterization of alterations. It is still the main method employed for monitoring patients with INMDs, either to evaluate the natural progression of the disease or to assess the response to treatment, as well as being used in order to screen family members for genetic counseling[3].

Discussion

Magnetic resonance imaging of the brain is considered the gold standard for evaluating diseases of central nervous system, as well as those of the cranial nerves. The use of three-dimensional (3D) steady-state free precession (SSFP) sequences, which are heavily T2-weighted, provides great contrast between the fine structures of the cranial nerves and the surrounding cerebrospinal fluid, allowing their cisternal segments to be identified. However, additional sequences are needed in order to assess the pattern of nerve disease, including contrast-enhanced T1-weighted sequences for the assessment of neuritis, as has been observed in the current pandemic, caused by infection with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2. Such sequences can also be used for the assessment of infectious processes and tumors, as well as for the assessment of congenital, traumatic, and vascular diseases of the cranial nerves, as

discussed and illustrated in the pictorial essay authored by Dalaqua et al, published in this issue of Radiologia Brasileira. The muscle fiber integrity in the muscle groups innervated by a given nerve can be evaluated in T1-weighted sequences, and short-tau inversion-recovery sequences can be used in order to map the extent of denervation, thus allowing the assessment not only of the anatomy of a nerve but also of its function[8]. Broadly interpreting the capabilities of MRI, this study confirms that the novel MR neurography sequence, also denoted as 3D CRANI , is a reliable and reproducible MR neurography technique for the visualisation of the extraforaminal cranial and occipital nerves. Previous studies already evaluated the feasibility of heavily T2-weighted MR imaging for nerve-specific visualization of the mandibular nerve but this is the first study to expand on this topic and evaluate the reliability of MRN in cranial and occipital nerve evaluation. Reliable imaging techniques are necessary when dealing with cranial nerve disorders, as electrophysiological and sensory examinations in the head and neck area have their own limitations. Some already described the advantageous role of MRN in diagnosing trigeminal nerve injuries and impact on clinical management. Within other domains such as brachial plexus imaging, MRN established its role and showed substantial therapeutic impact in over one third of patients[1]. This technical note successfully demonstrates the use of 3D CRANI, a modified black-blood STIR TSE sequence for nerve-selective imaging of peripheral cranial and spinal nerve branches. Diffusion-weighted prepulsing by MSDE for MR neurography purposes was first described by Yoneyama et al and further demonstrated for brachial plexus imaging by Klupp et al. This study is innovative in the sense that an MSDE pulse was applied in combination with a PSS sweep to further optimize nerve-enhanced imaging within clinically feasible acquisition times. The results from our study indicate excellent interobserver agreement[9-10]. Computed tomography of the skull base is also useful for assessing the course of the cranial nerves. The skull base foramina are the exits through which the nerves pass on their way to the structures of the face and neck. Knowledge of this anatomy and comparison with the contralateral side allow the assessment of bone

remodeling and irregularities, which can be related to conditions such as nerve sheath tumors. One thing that should be debated and further clarified is the radiological approach stipulated in the examination protocol. Due to bureaucratic and financial constraints, we seek to limit the examinations to a specific body segment, such as the skull, face, and orbits. Therefore, when there is a request for magnetic resonance imaging of the skull to evaluate paralysis of the third cranial nerve (oculomotor nerve), do we simply choose to include an SSFP sequence to evaluate the cisternal portion of this nerve, or do we decide to perform a complete analysis of its course, including sequences aimed at evaluating the cavernous sinus and orbit? We should reflect upon whether we really should work within the limits of the examination request or should expand our perspective and follow the entire path of the nerve in question[8].

Conclusion

In conclusion, to achieve an accurate and early diagnosis of cranial nerve diseases, it is essential for us as radiologists to utilize multiple complementary examination methods and strive to enhance the patient's quality of life.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. Casselman J, Van der Cruyssen F, Vanhove F, et al. 3D CRANI, a novel MR neurography sequence, can reliably visualise the extraforaminal cranial and occipital nerves. *Eur Radiol.* 2023;33:2861–70.
2. Cranial nerve schwannoma - A pictorial essay. Geethapriya S, Govindaraj J, Raghavan B, Ramakrishnan B, Arafath R, Vishwanathan S, Krishna M. *Indian J Radiol Imaging.* 2020 Apr-Jun;30(2):116-125. doi: 10.4103/ijri.IJRI_17_20. Epub 2020 Jul 13. PMID: 33100678
3. Inherited neurometabolic diseases and the importance of imaging-based classification systems. Ventura N. *Radiol Bras.* 2022 May-Jun;55(3):VII-VIII. doi: 10.1590/0100-3984.2022.55.3e2-en. PMID: 35795600

4. Imaging of cranial nerves: a pictorial overview. Romano N, Federici M, Castaldi A. *Insights Imaging*. 2019 Mar 15;10(1):33. doi: 10.1186/s13244-019-0719-5. PMID: 30877408
5. Lucas Lucio L, de Andrade Lourenção Freddi T. Glossopharyngeal, Vagus and Accessory Nerves: Anatomy and Pathology. *Semin Ultrasound CT MR*. 2023 Apr;44(2):95-103. doi: 10.1053/j.sult.2022.11.003. Epub 2022 Nov 13. PMID: 37055144.
6. Magnetic resonance imaging of the cranial nerves in congenital, traumatic, and vascular diseases: a pictorial essay. Dalaqua M, do Nascimento FBP, Miura LK, Reis F, Garcia MRT, Barbosa Júnior AA. *Radiol Bras*. 2021 May-Jun;54(3):185-192. doi: 10.1590/0100-3984.2020.0039. PMID: 34108766
7. Magnetic resonance imaging findings in diseases affecting the cranial nerves. Ribeiro BNF. *Radiol Bras*. 2022 Jan-Feb;55(1):V-VI. doi: 10.1590/0100-3984.2022.55.1e1. PMID: 35210667
8. The cranial nerves: extensions of the central nervous system or components of the peripheral nervous system - how should we evaluate them? Rueda-Lopes F. *Radiol Bras*. 2021 May-Jun;54(3):V-VI. doi: 10.1590/0100-3984.2021.54.3e1. PMID: 34108773
9. Van der Cruyssen F, Croonenborghs T-M, Hermans R, et al. 3D cranial nerve imaging, a novel MR neurography technique using black-blood STIR TSE with a pseudo steady-state sweep and motion-sensitized driven equilibrium pulse for the visualization of the extraforaminal cranial nerve branches. *Am J Neuroradiol*. 2021;42:578–80.
10. Van der Cruyssen F, Peeters F, Croonenborghs T-M, Fransen J, Renton T, Politis C, et al. A systematic review on diagnostic test accuracy of magnetic resonance neurography versus clinical neurosensory assessment for post-traumatic trigeminal neuropathy in patients reporting neurosensory disturbance. *Dentomaxillofac Radiol* 2020;: 20200103. doi: 10.1259/dmfr.20200103